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Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca

PRIN: PROGETTI DI RICERCA DI RILEVANTE INTERESSE NAZIONALE – Bando 2022 PNRR
Prot. P20224T9SK

PROMETEO

A **PRO**abilistic fra**ME**work for coas**T**al and harbor
d**E**fense in the c**O**ntext of climate change

D6.1

Four-monthly progress reports

WP6 - Management & Coordination

M6.1 - Project kick-off meeting

M6.2 - Project coordination and periodic and final project meeting

O1 – O2 – O3 – O4

Task 6.1 – Task 6.2

Leader RU: UniSALENTO

Participant RU: UniCT, UniNA, UniRC

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February 2026

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1. Introduction

The management and coordination activities of WP6 were fundamental to the successful implementation of the project activities, ensuring they were carried out effectively and within the established timeframe. This document reports the progress report produced during the course of the project. Below is the list of the reports:

- I four-month period: December 2023 - March 2024;
- II four-month period: April 2024 - July 2024;
- III four-month period: August 2024 - November 2024;
- IV four-month period: December 2024 - March 2025;
- V four-month period: April 2025 - July 2025;
- VI period: August 2025 - February 2026.

The progress reports collected in the present deliverable demonstrate that milestone M6.2 (project coordination and periodic and final project meeting) has been produced.

2. I four-month period: December 2023 -
March 2024

FRAMEWORK TECHNICAL -SCIENTIFIC REPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTING ENTITY

PROMETEO - A PRObabilistic fraMEwork for coasTal and harbor dEfense in the cOntext of climate change (prot. P20224T9SK)

NATIONAL RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE PLAN (NRRP) – MISSION 4 COMPONENT 2 INVESTMENT 1.1 – “Fund for the National Research Program and for Projects of National Interest (NRP)”

INTRODUCTION

The Technical-Scientific Report is produced by the *Principal Investigator*, on the basis of a discussion with each local manager for the purposes of collecting data and documenting the progress of each operational unit. It is then submitted according to deadlines envisaged in the related notification.

The Report is composed of the following sections:

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT, where information on the general trends of the projects are included by making reference to the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, to the compliance with the project activities, to the *DNSH* and *Open Access* principles as per the approved project.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES, which entails the description of carried out activities based on the details provided by the operational units involved in the implementation of the project during the collaboration period. It also includes the description of future activities, potential publications and challenges encountered as well as actions for improvement. This, in order to guarantee the achievement of goals that have been established when the financed project was presented.

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS, where EU common indicators connected to the specific investment should be enhanced.

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS, regards the forecast scenario on the development of the project and final comments.

The hereby provided scheme will also be used when presenting the final results of the implemented activities within the project financed by the Ministry.

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT

With regard to the specific timeframe (30th of November 2023-31st of March 2024), it is below provided:

- a) a brief summary of the project;

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty of describing their response to wave loads as well as including the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans. In this context, uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. Based on the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations, a probabilistic calculation procedure will be defined for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions, focusing on the Italian situation. The characterization of climate forcing, which will be carried out through a multivariate analysis, will include the combined effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels provided by available projection models. Moreover, current knowledge on the resistance of defense solutions will be improved through the analysis of new and existing experimental and numerical datasets, focusing on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. Finally, easy-to-use performance and economic indexes will be defined to facilitate the use of the project findings by designers and decision-makers. The main expected impacts of PROMETEO are the improvement of current design practices and significant inputs for the revision and the update of the current Italian design guidelines.

The activities are organized in six work packages (hereinafter referred to as WP), each one focused on the objectives reported above. In particular, WP1 builds the foundation of the project based on a critical analysis of the current state of art, whereas WP2 develops the probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions. WP3 and WP4 support WP2, through the statistical treatment of met-ocean data and the experimental and numerical data on failure mechanisms, respectively. The development of web-based practical tools and the dissemination of the project results is carried out in WP5. Finally, coordination, management and monitoring are carried out in

WP6. The results of each WP are organized and presented in deliverables (D), milestones (M) and targets (T), achieved through specific tasks.

b) names of the operational units involved in the implementation of the project;

The research units (RUs) involved in the implementation of the project are:

- Università degli Studi di Catania (UniCT),
- Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (UniNA),
- Università degli Studi "Mediterranea" di Reggio Calabria (UniRC),
- Università del Salento (UniSALENTO).

c) description of the achievement of the objectives connected to the project and related outcomes;

The activities carried out during the first four-monthly period regarded:

- Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 of WP1;
- Task 2.1 of WP2;
- Task 3.1 of WP3;
- Task 4.1 of WP4;
- Task 5.1 of WP5;
- Task 6.1 and 6.2 of WP6.

WP1

The tasks of WP1, which consist in the critical review of design approaches and formulations for coastal and harbor defense solutions (i.e. rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments) as well as their possible upgrading options, aim to the specific objective O1, which is the comparative analysis of existing international regulations and guidelines for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions, in order to identify gaps in the current state of art of the probabilistic design approach. The achievement of the specific objective O1 and of the corresponding milestone M1.1 will be finalized with the drafting of the deliverable D1.1, which is currently ongoing.

WP2

Task 2.1 of WP2 consists in the development of a level III procedure based on the Monte Carlo simulation technique to calculate the failure probability of the system, directly contributing to the achievement of the specific objective O2.1. The ongoing activities will allow to address the milestone M2.1 and provide a fundamental contribution for the drafting of the deliverable D2.1.

WP3

Task 3.1 of WP3 consists in the collection of historical and future projection met-ocean datasets, which is fundamental to achieve the specific objective O3.1, namely the probabilistic characterization of hydrodynamic loads acting on harbor and coastal defense solutions based on multivariate analysis, also including the effects of climate change. In particular, the activities carried out so far will contribute to the achievement of the milestone M3.1 and the target T3.1 as well as to the drafting of the deliverable D3.1.

WP4

Task 4.1 of WP4 consists in the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. The ongoing activities related to this task will contribute to the

achievement of the corresponding specific objective O3.2 and the milestone M4.1, as well as to the drafting of the deliverable D4.1.

WP5

Task 5.1 of WP5 consists in the creation of the web-platform to foster the usability of the project results and improve planning and design practice. The ongoing activities related to this task will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.1 and the milestone M5.1. The web-platform itself will be the deliverable D5.1.

WP6

Finally, the tasks of WP6 support management and coordination, and hence the corresponding activities, which will be continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project, are fundamental for the achievement of each specific objective of the project. The milestone M6.1 has been completed with the organization of the project kick-off meeting, whereas coordination activities have been carried out to reach the milestone M6.2 at the end of the project. Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 will contain the four-monthly progress reports and the meeting minutes, respectively.

- d) description of the carried out activities which are in compliance with the *DNSH*, *Open Access* principles as well as with *gender*, *generational* principles and with those of *Equal opportunities*

The activities carried out during the first four-monthly period consisted in:

- the critical review of the state of the art and the drafting of the deliverable D1.1;
- the definition of the theoretical basis for the setup of the probabilistic framework;
- the collection of existing met-ocean datasets;
- the definition of analysis procedure;
- the organization of the project kick-off meeting.

All these activities do not require interactions with the environment, and hence they are in compliance with the DNSH principle, since they do not affect the six environmental objectives indicated by the in art. 17 of the EU regulation 2020/852 in any way. In this regard, it should be noted that the final results of the project will contribute to the achievement of the second environmental objective, namely the adaptation to climate change. The Open Access principles are also observed, particularly referring to the development of the project web-platform and to the consequent free availability of the project data and results, as well as to the planned production of open-access scientific papers. The respect of the gender and generational and of equal opportunities principles is ensured by the varied composition of project team. In particular, despite coastal engineering is a traditional male working environment, the project team includes also female researchers, among which the Principal Investigator and the Substitute Principal Investigator of the project. Moreover, both male and female young researchers participate to the project activities under the guidance of the senior members of the group.

- e) description of the actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge

The actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge belong to the WP5. In particular, the procedure to entrust the creation of the project web-platform to a specialized third company has been started. Moreover, a preliminary discussion for the organization of future workshops with relevant stakeholders, which will be carried out during the next four-monthly periods, has been held during the kick-off meeting, held in Catania on the 18th of December 2023.

The research group is presently working on some journal publications of the work. The group will also present the project and the ongoing activities during the next two main international and national conferences:

- the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions, which will take place in Parma, 15th -18th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Framework Probabilistico Per La Progettazione Di Soluzioni Di Difesa Costiera E Portuale In Un Contesto Di Cambiamenti Climatici;*
- the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions, which will take place in Parma, 15th -18th September 2024, with the following contribution: *L'incertezza Idrodinamica Nella Progettazione Delle Scogliere Frangiflutti In Massi Naturali;*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Spatial assessment of the failure probability of rubble-mound breakwaters*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *On The Uncertainties In Rock-armoured Breakwaters Stability*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Wave overtopping at vertical walls in shallow water conditions: a predictive formula*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Vertical seawalls protected by rubble mound structures: prediction tools and physical insight*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Interactions between river and coastal sedimentary balance and effects of hydraulic works on the shoreline changes.*
- the 17th International Coastal Symposium (ICS2024) which will take place in Doha, 24th-27th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Analytical solutions for bounded beaches: enhancing coastal management strategies and beach fill project*

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES

With regard to the specific timeframe (bi-monthly/end of project activities), it is below provided:

- a) detailed description of activities carried out by each operational unit with a focus on the timeframe for their implementation

The activities related to Task 1.1, Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 (WP1) are carried out by all the involved RUs. The critical analysis of existing design regulations, the collection of design formulas, and the review of possible adaptation solutions is performed for all the coastal defense structures considered in the project, namely rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. The documents used for the analyses are design codes, regulations and recommendations of various countries and international scientific papers. The research activities are distributed as follows:

- UniCT focuses on rubble-mound breakwaters;
- UniNA focuses on vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments;
- UniRC focuses on vertical breakwaters;
- UniSALENTO (leader RU) focuses on rubble-mound breakwaters and artificial beach nourishments.

The activities related to the Task 2.1 (WP2) are carried out by UniCT (leader RU) and UniSALENTO. The theoretical basis of the algorithm for the calculation of the failure probability of the system have been defined, and a first version of the programming codes for the implantation of Monte Carlo simulations has been drafted.

The activities related to the Task 3.1 (WP3) are carried out by UniNA and UniRC who are collecting existing met-ocean historical (measured or reanalysis) and projection scenarios, also assessing their reliability and mutual consistency. In particular, different wind, wind waves, sea level, precipitations datasets, from ISPRA, Copernicus Climate Data Service, and other sources, etc are considered.

The activities related to the Task 4.1 (WP4) are carried out by UniCT and UniNA (leader RU). The involved RUs have started to dialogue with relevant stakeholder to collect project documents and experiences on the design of adaptation options of coastal and harbor defense solutions, useful for the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options.

The activities related to the Task 5.1 (WP5) are carried out by UniCT and UniSALENTO (leader RU). UniCT requested the financial advance to the University of Catania to start the procedure to entrust the creation of the project web-platform to a specialized third company.

The activities related to Task 6.1, Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 (WP6) are carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniCT the leader RU. The scientific and administrative management of the project (e.g. reporting, coordination, etc.) for technical development and financial monitoring is continuously performed by all the RUs. The project kick-off meeting took place on 18/12/2023 at the University of Catania, and hence the milestone M6.1 has been achieved as planned. During the meeting, representatives of all the RU presented their research experiences consistent with the project and proposed suggestions for the development of the activities of the WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5. Moreover, the RUs discussed the

organization of the first workshop with stakeholders, which will take place during the next four-monthly periods.

- b) description of potential changes to what has been originally approved mentioning the impacts on the aim of the intervention, on the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, on the proposed actions for improvement;

The project activities are proceeding according to the time schedule, and hence no changes to the approved project are planned.

- c) description of potential challenges encountered and of the proposed actions for improvement;

Some challenges have been faced only for the development of the activities related to the task 5.1, i.e. to the creation of the project web-platform. In particular, the financial advance payment requested to the University of Catania to entrust the creation of the project web-platform to a specialized third company has been received only in February 2024, due to uncompressible administrative times. In any case, the task 5.1 will be completed according to the time schedule of the project.

UniSALENTO also requested the financial advance payment to the University of Salento to advertise a 12-month research grant, which was concluded in February 2024. The new grantee started on March 1st, 2024.

- d) brief description of potential publications.

Even though the publication of open access papers and the participation to national or international conferences are planned starting from the second four-monthly period, some future research works are already under preparation. In the context of the WP4, UniCT will produce a paper on the description of the hydraulic response of rubble-mound breakwaters in terms of wave overtopping, based on both experimental and numerical results. Moreover, UniCT will present a work related to the activities of the WP2 entitled *Spatial assessment of the failure probability of rubble-mound breakwaters* at the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) in Rome (8th-14th September 2024). UniSALENTO will also present a contribution, entitled *On The Uncertainties In Rock-armoured Breakwaters Stability*. UniNa will also present two contributions, entitled *Wave overtopping at vertical walls in shallow water conditions: a predictive formula* and *Vertical seawalls protected by rubble mound structures: prediction tools and physical insight*. UNIRC will present a contribution named *Interactions between river and coastal sedimentary balance and effects of hydraulic works on the shoreline changes*.

A work related to the general description of the project and of the first results entitled *Framework probabilistico per la progettazione di soluzioni di difesa costiera e portuale in un contesto di cambiamenti climatici* will be also presented by all the RUs at the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions (XXXIX Convegno Nazionale di Idraulica e Costruzioni Idrauliche) in Parma (15th-18th September 2024). UniSALENTO will

also present a contribution at the entitled *L'incertezza Idrodinamica Nella Progettazione Delle Scogliere Frangiflutti In Massi Naturali*.

A work related to the first results of the project entitled *Analytical solutions for bounded beaches: enhancing coastal management strategies and beach fill project* will be also presented by UniNA at the International Coastal Symposium (ICS 2024) in Doha (24th-27th September 2024).

Any relevant attached document which includes the abovementioned details

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS

Below the updates on the indicator RRFCI 8 – “*Number of researchers who work in research centres which are recipients of financial support (women; men; non-binary)*” – as per the description in the guidelines included in the n.34 MEF notification from the 17th of October 2022.

Common indicators	Planned value	Implemented value
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (women)	3	3
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (men)	7	7
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (non-binary)	0	0

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS

Below it is provided a description of the forecast scenario on the development of the project, any potential change which is deemed necessary for the future as well as comments on the document.

1) Predictive analysis

The project activities are expected to progress according to the time schedule. In particular, in the next four-monthly period all the RU will continue the activities related to the tasks of the WP1. In the context of WP2, UniCT and UniSALENTO will work on the algorithm for the probabilistic calculations. UniNA and UniRC will carry on the activities of WP3 related to the creation of a database of met-ocean data for the Italian coastal areas. For the WP4, UniCT and UniNa will continue to work on the definition a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions. UniCT and UniSALENTO will go on working on the creation of the project web-platform included in the WP5. Finally, all the tasks of the WP6 are continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project.

2) Final comments

Currently, the project activities are proceeding as planned during the proposal submission and approval phases. Therefore, no changes to the scheduled activities and/or corrective actions for redefining the stated objectives are anticipated.

Legal Representative

(digital signature)

ATTACHMENTS

The below documents are also attached to the technical – scientific report:

Att.1 – Declaration of compliance with DNSH principle and compliance with other principles as per the Environment code;

3. Il four-month period: April 2024 - July 2024

FRAMEWORK TECHNICAL -SCIENTIFIC REPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTING ENTITY

PROMETEO - A PRObabilistic fraMEwork for coasTal and harbor dEfense in the cOntext of climate change (prot. P20224T9SK)

NATIONAL RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE PLAN (NRRP) – MISSION 4 COMPONENT 2 INVESTMENT 1.1 – “Fund for the National Research Program and for Projects of National Interest (NRP)”

INTRODUCTION

The Technical-Scientific Report is produced by the *Principal Investigator*, on the basis of a discussion with each local manager for the purposes of collecting data and documenting the progress of each operational unit. It is then submitted according to deadlines envisaged in the related notification.

The Report is composed of the following sections:

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT, where information on the general trends of the projects are included by making reference to the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, to the compliance with the project activities, to the *DNSH* and *Open Access* principles as per the approved project.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES, which entails the description of carried out activities based on the details provided by the operational units involved in the implementation of the project during the collaboration period. It also includes the description of future activities, potential publications and challenges encountered as well as actions for improvement. This, in order to guarantee the achievement of goals that have been established when the financed project was presented.

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS, where EU common indicators connected to the specific investment should be enhanced.

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS, regards the forecast scenario on the development of the project and final comments.

The hereby provided scheme will also be used when presenting the final results of the implemented activities within the project financed by the Ministry.

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT

With regard to the specific timeframe (1st of April 2024-31st of July 2024), it is below provided:

- a) a brief summary of the project;

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty of describing their response to wave loads as well as including the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans. In this context, uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. Based on the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations, a probabilistic calculation procedure will be defined for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions, focusing on the Italian situation. The characterization of climate forcing, which will be carried out through a multivariate analysis, will include the combined effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels provided by available projection models. Moreover, current knowledge on the resistance of defense solutions will be improved through the analysis of new and existing experimental and numerical datasets, focusing on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. Finally, easy-to-use performance and economic indexes will be defined to facilitate the use of the project findings by designers and decision-makers. The main expected impacts of PROMETEO are the improvement of current design practices and significant inputs for the revision and the update of the current Italian design guidelines.

The activities are organized in six work packages (hereinafter referred to as WP), each one focused on the objectives reported above. In particular, WP1 builds the foundation of the project based on a critical analysis of the current state of art, whereas WP2 develops the probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions. WP3 and WP4 support WP2, through the statistical treatment of met-ocean data and the experimental and numerical data on failure mechanisms, respectively. The development of web-based practical tools and the dissemination of the project results is carried out in WP5. Finally, coordination, management and monitoring are carried out in

WP6. The results of each WP are organized and presented in deliverables (D), milestones (M) and targets (T), achieved through specific tasks.

b) names of the operational units involved in the implementation of the project;

The research units (RUs) involved in the implementation of the project are:

- Università degli Studi di Catania (UniCT),
- Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (UniNA),
- Università degli Studi "Mediterranea" di Reggio Calabria (UniRC),
- Università del Salento (UniSALENTO).

c) description of the achievement of the objectives connected to the project and related outcomes;

The activities carried out during the second four-monthly period regarded:

- Tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 of WP1;
- Task 2.1 of WP2;
- Task 3.1 of WP3;
- Task 4.1 of WP4;
- Task 5.1, Task 5.2 and Task 5.3 of WP5;
- Task 6.1 and 6.2 of WP6.

WP1

The tasks of WP1, which consist in the critical review of design approaches and formulations for coastal and harbor defense solutions (i.e. rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments) as well as their possible upgrading options, aim to the specific objective O1, which is the comparative analysis of existing international regulations and guidelines for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions, in order to identify gaps in the current state of art of the probabilistic design approach. The achievement of the specific objective O1 and of the corresponding milestone M1.1 has been finalized with the drafting of the deliverable D1.1.

WP2

Task 2.1 of WP2 consists in the development of a level III procedure based on the Monte Carlo simulation technique to calculate the failure probability of the system, directly contributing to the achievement of the specific objective O2.1. The ongoing activities will allow to address the milestone M2.1 and provide a fundamental contribution for the drafting of the deliverable D2.1.

WP3

Task 3.1 of WP3 consists in the collection of historical and future projection met-ocean datasets, whereas Task 3.2 of WP3 consists in the downscaling of such datasets at sites of interest. Both tasks are fundamental to achieve the specific objective O3.1, namely the probabilistic characterization of hydrodynamic loads acting on harbor and coastal defense solutions based on multivariate analysis, also including the effects of climate change. In particular, the activities carried out so far will contribute to the achievement of the milestone M3.1 and the target T3.1 as well as to the drafting of the deliverable D3.1.

WP4

Task 4.1 of WP4 consists in the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. Task 4.2 of WP4 consists in the comparative analysis of failure

mechanisms of rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. Moreover, in the frame of Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6, they provide useful insight to plan new experimental and numerical activities and to collect existing experimental and numerical datasets on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. The ongoing activities related to these tasks will contribute to the achievement of the corresponding specific objectives O3.2 and O3.3 and of the milestone M4.1 and of the target T4.1, as well as to the drafting of the deliverable D4.1.

WP5

Task 5.1 of WP5 consists in the creation of the web-platform to foster the usability of the project results and improve planning and design practice. The ongoing activities related to these tasks will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.1 and the milestone M5.1. The web-platform itself will be the deliverable D5.1. Task 5.2 of WP5 consists in the organization of workshops, meetings with relevant stakeholders and dissemination events. The ongoing activities related to these tasks will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.2, the milestone M5.2, and the target T5.1, as well as to the drafting of the deliverable D5.2. Task 5.3 of WP5 consists in the production of scientific publications and the participation to international or national conferences. The ongoing activities related to this task will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective 4.2, the milestone M5.3 and the targets T5.2 and T5.3.

WP6

Finally, the tasks of WP6 support management and coordination, and hence the corresponding activities, which will be continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project, are fundamental for the achievement of each specific objective of the project. The milestone M6.1 has been completed with the organization of the project kick-off meeting, whereas coordination activities have been carried out to reach the milestone M6.2 at the end of the project. Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 will contain the four-monthly progress reports and the meeting minutes, respectively.

- d) description of the carried out activities which are in compliance with the *DNSH*, *Open Access* principles as well as with *gender*, *generational* principles and with those of *Equal opportunities*

The activities carried out during the second four-monthly period consisted in:

- the critical review of the state of the art and the drafting of the deliverable D1.1;
- the definition of the theoretical basis for the setup of the probabilistic framework;
- the collection of existing met-ocean datasets;
- the definition of analysis procedure;
- the organization of a meeting with stakeholders.

All these activities do not require interactions with the environment, and hence they are in compliance with the DNSH principle, since they do not affect the six environmental objectives indicated by the in art. 17 of the EU regulation 2020/852 in any way. In this regard, it should be noted that the final results of the project will contribute to the achievement of the second environmental objective, namely the adaptation to climate change. The Open Access principles are also observed, particularly referring to the development of the project web-platform and to the consequent free availability of the project data and results, as well as to the planned production of open-access scientific papers. The respect of the gender and generational and of equal opportunities principles is ensured by the varied composition of project team. In particular, despite coastal engineering is a traditional male working

environment, the project team includes also female researchers, among which the Principal Investigator and the Substitute Principal Investigator of the project. Moreover, both male and female young researchers participate to the project activities under the guidance of the senior members of the group.

e) description of the actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge

The actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge belong to the WP5. In particular, the creation of the project web-platform is in the process of being entrusted to a specialized third company. Moreover, a workshop with relevant stakeholders has been organized and took place on the 23/05/2024 in Rome.

The research group is presently working on some journal publications of the work and one has been already published (*Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., & Saponieri, A. (2024). Laboratory investigation on pore pressures inside a rubble mound breakwater in depth-limited waters. Applied Ocean Research, 147, 103988*), with acknowledgement to the project. The group will also present the project and the ongoing activities during the next two main international and national conferences:

- the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions, which will take place in Parma, 15th -18th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Framework Probabilistico Per La Progettazione Di Soluzioni Di Difesa Costiera E Portuale In Un Contesto Di Cambiamenti Climatici;*
- the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions, which will take place in Parma, 15th -18th September 2024, with the following contribution: *L'incertezza Idrodinamica Nella Progettazione Delle Scogliere Frangiflutti In Massi Naturali;*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Spatial assessment of the failure probability of rubble-mound breakwaters*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *On The Uncertainties In Rock-armoured Breakwaters Stability*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Wave overtopping at vertical walls in shallow water conditions: a predictive formula*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Vertical seawalls protected by rubble mound structures: prediction tools and physical insight.*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which will take place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Interactions between river and coastal sedimentary balance and effects of hydraulic works on the shoreline changes.*
- the 17th International Coastal Symposium (ICS2024) which will take place in Doha, 24th-27th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Analytical solutions for bounded beaches: enhancing coastal management strategies and beach fill project*

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES

With regard to the specific timeframe (bi-monthly/end of project activities), it is below provided:

- a) detailed description of activities carried out by each operational unit with a focus on the timeframe for their implementation

The activities related to Task 1.1, Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 (WP1) have been carried out by all the involved RUs are now completed. According to the project time schedule, the milestone M1.1 has been achieved and the deliverable D1.1 has been produced. The critical analysis of existing design regulations, the collection of design formulas, and the review of possible adaptation solutions was performed for all the coastal defense structures considered in the project, namely rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. The documents used for the analyses were design codes, regulations and recommendations of various countries and international scientific papers. The research activities were distributed as follows:

- UniCT focused on rubble-mound breakwaters;
- UniNA focused on vertical breakwaters, seawalls, and artificial beach nourishments;
- UniRC focused on vertical breakwaters;
- UniSALENTO (leader RU) focused on rubble-mound breakwaters and artificial beach nourishments.

The activities related to the Task 2.1 (WP2) are carried out by UniCT (leader RU) and UniSALENTO. The theoretical basis of the algorithm for the calculation of the failure probability of the system have been defined, and a first version of the programming codes for the implantation of Monte Carlo simulations has been drafted.

The activities related to the Task 3.1 (WP3) are carried out by UniNA and UniRC who are collecting existing met-ocean historical (measured or reanalysis) and projection scenarios, also assessing their reliability and mutual consistency. In particular, different wind, wind waves, sea level, precipitations datasets, from ISPRA, Copernicus Climate Data Service, and other sources, etc are considered.

The activities related to the Task 4.1 (WP4) have been carried out by UniCT and UniNA (leader RU). The involved RUs collected project documents and experiences on the design of adaptation options of coastal and harbor defense solutions, useful for the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. The activities related to the Task 4.2 (WP4) are carried out by UniRC and UniSALENTO. The activities related to Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6 are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, Rus are collecting existing experimental and numerical data on damaged and upgraded harbor rubble-mound breakwaters, which includes both structure damage and wave overtopping, vertical wall breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments, considering their own data and available literature data.

The activities related to the Task 5.1 (WP5) are carried out by UniCT and UniSALENTO (leader RU). The creation of the project web-platform is going to be entrusted to a specialized third company by UniCT. The activities related to the Task 5.2 (WP5) are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, during this four-monthly period the RUs organized a meeting

with contractors, designers, and construction companies which work in field of coastal and harbor defense solutions. The meeting was entitled “*Spunti innovativi per la progettazione delle opere marittime – verso le nuove Istruzioni Tecniche*” and it took place on 23/05/2024 at the *Università degli Studi Link*, in Rome. More than 60 people participated to the event. During the meeting a questionnaire has been submitted to the stakeholders in order to collect their needs and suggestions. The activities related to the Task 5.3 (WP5) are carried out by all the involved RUs. Specifically, during this four-month period UniSALENTO published the work *Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., & Saponieri, A. (2024). Laboratory investigation on pore pressures inside a rubble mound breakwater in depth-limited waters. Applied Ocean Research, 147, 103988.*

The activities related to Task 6.1, Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 (WP6) are carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniCT the leader RU. The scientific and administrative management of the project (e.g. reporting, coordination, etc.) for technical development and financial monitoring is continuously performed by all the RUs.

- b) description of potential changes to what has been originally approved mentioning the impacts on the aim of the intervention, on the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, on the proposed actions for improvement;

The project activities are proceeding according to the time schedule, and hence no changes to the approved project are planned.

- c) description of potential challenges encountered and of the proposed actions for improvement;

Some challenges are still faced only for the development of the activities related to the task 5.1, i.e. to the creation of the project web-platform. In particular, the tender for proposal has been issued and the contract should be signed in the coming months.

- d) brief description of potential publications.

Based on the preparation of deliverable D1.1: Report on existing regulations and guidelines for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions, main existing formulations for the description of failure mechanisms and options for adaptation to climate change., a joint publication is under preparation. In the context of the WP4, UniCT will produce a paper on the description of the hydraulic response of rubble-mound breakwaters in terms of wave overtopping, based on both experimental and numerical results. Moreover, UniCT will present a work related to the activities of the WP2 entitled *Spatial assessment of the failure probability of rubble-mound breakwaters* at the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) in Rome (8th-14th September 2024). UniSALENTO has already published the journal-indexed paper: *Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., & Saponieri, A. (2024). Laboratory investigation on pore pressures inside a rubble mound breakwater in depth-limited waters. Applied Ocean Research, 147, 103988*, with acknowledgement to the project. UniSALENTO will also present a contribution, entitled *On The Uncertainties In Rock-armoured Breakwaters Stability*. UniNa will also present two contributions, entitled *Wave overtopping at vertical walls in shallow water conditions: a predictive formula* and *Vertical seawalls protected by rubble mound structures: prediction tools and physical insight*. UNIRC will present a contribution named

Interactions between river and coastal sedimentary balance and effects of hydraulic works on the shoreline changes.

A work related to the general description of the project and of the first results entitled *Framework probabilistico per la progettazione di soluzioni di difesa costiera e portuale in un contesto di cambiamenti climatici* will be also presented by all the RUs at the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions (XXXIX Convegno Nazionale di Idraulica e Costruzioni Idrauliche) in Parma (15th-18th September 2024). UniSALENTO will also present a contribution at the entitled *L'incertezza Idrodinamica Nella Progettazione Delle Scogliere Frangiflutti In Massi Naturali*.

A work related to the first results of the project entitled *Analytical solutions for bounded beaches: enhancing coastal management strategies and beach fill project* will be also presented by UniNA at the International Coastal Symposium (ICS 2024) in Doha (24th-27th September 2024).

Any relevant attached document which includes the abovementioned details

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS

Below the updates on the indicator RRFCI 8 – “*Number of researchers who work in research centres which are recipients of financial support (women; men; non-binary)*” – as per the description in the guidelines included in the n.34 MEF notification from the 17th of October 2022.

Common indicators	Planned value	Implemented value
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (women)	3	3
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (men)	7	7
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (non-binary)	0	0

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS

Below it is provided a description of the forecast scenario on the development of the project, any potential change which is deemed necessary for the future as well as comments on the document.

1) Predictive analysis

The project activities are expected to progress according to the time schedule. In particular, in the next four-monthly UniCT and UniSALENTO continue to work on the algorithm for the probabilistic calculations. UniNA and UniRC will carry on the activities of WP3 related to the creation of a database of met-ocean data for the Italian coastal areas and they will start the activities related to Multivariate analysis of wave climate and sea levels. For the WP4, UniRC and UniSALENTO will continue to work on the comparative analysis of failure mechanisms of both conventional and adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions. In the meantime, all the involved RUs will carry on the activities related to the collection of both new and existing experimental and numerical datasets on the performance of rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments. For the WP5, UniCT and UniSALENTO will go on working on the creation of the project web-platform, whereas all the involved RUs will continue to organize meetings with stakeholders and dissemination events, as well as to work on scientific publications. Finally, all the tasks of the WP6 are continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project.

2) Final comments

Currently, the project activities are proceeding as planned during the proposal submission and approval phases. Therefore, no changes to the scheduled activities and/or corrective actions for redefining the stated objectives are anticipated.

The Delegate of the Rector for the Research

(digital signature)

ATTACHMENTS

The below documents are also attached to the technical – scientific report:

Att.1 – Declaration of compliance with DNSH principle and compliance with other principles as per the Environment code;

4. III four-month period: August 2024 -
November 2024

FRAMEWORK TECHNICAL -SCIENTIFIC REPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTING ENTITY

PROMETEO - A PRObabilistic fraMEwork for coasTal and harbor dEfense in the cOntext of climate change (prot. P20224T9SK)

NATIONAL RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE PLAN (NRRP) – MISSION 4 COMPONENT 2 INVESTMENT 1.1 – “Fund for the National Research Program and for Projects of National Interest (NRP)”

INTRODUCTION

The Technical-Scientific Report is produced by the *Principal Investigator*, on the basis of a discussion with each local manager for the purposes of collecting data and documenting the progress of each operational unit. It is then submitted according to deadlines envisaged in the related notification.

The Report is composed of the following sections:

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT, where information on the general trends of the projects are included by making reference to the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, to the compliance with the project activities, to the *DNSH* and *Open Access* principles as per the approved project.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES, which entails the description of carried out activities based on the details provided by the operational units involved in the implementation of the project during the collaboration period. It also includes the description of future activities, potential publications and challenges encountered as well as actions for improvement. This, in order to guarantee the achievement of goals that have been established when the financed project was presented.

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS, where EU common indicators connected to the specific investment should be enhanced.

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS, regards the forecast scenario on the development of the project and final comments.

The hereby provided scheme will also be used when presenting the final results of the implemented activities within the project financed by the Ministry.

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT

With regard to the specific timeframe (1st of August 2024-30th of November 2024), it is below provided:

- a) a brief summary of the project;

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty of describing their response to wave loads as well as including the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans. In this context, uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. Based on the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations, a probabilistic calculation procedure will be defined for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions, focusing on the Italian situation. The characterization of climate forcing, which will be carried out through a multivariate analysis, will include the combined effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels provided by available projection models. Moreover, current knowledge on the resistance of defense solutions will be improved through the analysis of new and existing experimental and numerical datasets, focusing on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. Finally, easy-to-use performance and economic indexes will be defined to facilitate the use of the project findings by designers and decision-makers. The main expected impacts of PROMETEO are the improvement of current design practices and significant inputs for the revision and the update of the current Italian design guidelines.

The activities are organized in six work packages (hereinafter referred to as WP), each one focused on the objectives reported above. In particular, WP1 builds the foundation of the project based on a critical analysis of the current state of art, whereas WP2 develops the probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions. WP3 and WP4 support WP2, through the statistical treatment of met-ocean data and the experimental and numerical data on failure mechanisms, respectively. The development of web-based practical tools and the dissemination of the project results is carried out in WP5. Finally, coordination, management and monitoring are carried out in

WP6. The results of each WP are organized and presented in deliverables (D), milestones (M) and targets (T), achieved through specific tasks.

b) names of the operational units involved in the implementation of the project;

The research units (RUs) involved in the implementation of the project are:

- Università degli Studi di Catania (UniCT),
- Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (UniNA),
- Università degli Studi "Mediterranea" di Reggio Calabria (UniRC),
- Università del Salento (UniSALENTO).

c) description of the achievement of the objectives connected to the project and related outcomes;

The activities carried out during the third four-monthly period regarded:

- Task 2.1, Task 2.2 and Task 2.3 of WP2;
- Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 of WP3;
- Task 4.2, Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5 and Task 4.6 of WP4;
- Task 5.1, Task 5.2 and Task 5.3 of WP5;
- Task 6.1 and 6.2 of WP6.

WP2

Task 2.1 of WP2 consists in the development of a level III procedure based on the Monte Carlo simulation technique to calculate the failure probability of the system, Task 2.2 consist in the definition of performance and economic indexes useful to compare different adaptation solutions and climate scenarios, and Task 2.3 consist in the application of the probabilistic methodology to case studies. The three tasks directly contribute to the achievement of the specific objectives O2.1, O2.2 and O2.3, respectively. The ongoing activities will allow to address the milestones M2.1 and M2.2 and the target T2.1, as well as the drafting of the deliverable D2.1.

WP3

Task 3.2 of WP3 consists in the downscaling of such historical and future projection met-ocean datasets collected during the Task 3.1 at sites of interest, whereas Task 3.3 consists in the multivariate analysis of such downscaled data. Both tasks are fundamental to achieve the specific objectives O2.3 and O3.1, namely the validation of the proposed probabilistic methodology through application to emblematic case studies and the probabilistic characterization of hydrodynamic loads acting on harbor and coastal defense solutions based on multivariate analysis, also including the effects of climate change. In particular, the activities carried out so far will contribute to the achievement of the milestones M3.1, M3.2 and M2.2 and the targets T3.1 and T2.1 as well as to the drafting of the deliverables D3.1 and D2.1.

WP4

Task 4.2 of WP4 consists in the comparative analysis of failure mechanisms of rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. In the frame of Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6, it provides useful insight to plan new experimental and numerical activities and to collect existing experimental and numerical datasets on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. The ongoing activities related to these five tasks will contribute to the achievement of the corresponding

specific objectives O3.2, O3.3 and O2.3 and of milestones M4.1, M4.2 and M2.2 and of the targets T4.1 and T2.1, as well as to the drafting of the deliverables D4.1 and D2.1.

WP5

Task 5.1 of WP5 consists in the creation of the web-platform to foster the usability of the project results and improve planning and design practice. The ongoing activities related to these tasks will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.1 and the milestone M5.1. The web-platform itself will be the deliverable D5.1. Task 5.2 of WP5 consists in the organization of workshops, meetings with relevant stakeholders and dissemination events. The ongoing activities related to these tasks will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.2, the milestone M5.2, and the target T5.1, as well as to the drafting of the deliverable D5.2. Task 5.3 of WP5 consists in the production of scientific publications and the participation to international or national conferences. The ongoing activities related to this task will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective 4.2, the milestone M5.3 and the targets T5.2 and T5.3.

WP6

Finally, the tasks of WP6 support management and coordination, and hence the corresponding activities, which will be continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project, are fundamental for the achievement of each specific objective of the project. The milestone M6.1 has been completed with the organization of the project kick-off meeting, whereas coordination activities have been carried out to reach the milestone M6.2 at the end of the project. Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 will contain the four-monthly progress reports and the meeting minutes, respectively.

- d) description of the carried out activities which are in compliance with the *DNSH*, *Open Access* principles as well as with *gender*, *generational* principles and with those of *Equal opportunities*

The activities carried out during the third four-monthly period consisted in:

- the definition of the theoretical basis for the setup of the probabilistic framework;
- the definition of performance indexes;
- the downscaling of existing met-ocean datasets;
- the definition of analysis procedures;
- the performance of experimental and numerical tests;
- the organization of a project meeting.

All these activities do not require interactions with the environment, and hence they are in compliance with the DNSH principle, since they do not affect the six environmental objectives indicated by the in art. 17 of the EU regulation 2020/852 in any way. In this regard, it should be noted that the final results of the project will contribute to the achievement of the second environmental objective, namely the adaptation to climate change. The Open Access principles are also observed, particularly referring to the development of the project web-platform and to the consequent free availability of the project data and results, as well as to the planned production of open-access scientific papers. The respect of the gender and generational and of equal opportunities principles is ensured by the varied composition of project team. In particular, despite coastal engineering is a traditional male working environment, the project team includes also female researchers, among which the Principal Investigator and the Substitute Principal Investigator of the project. Moreover, both male and female young researchers participate to the project activities under the guidance of the senior members of the group.

e) description of the actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge

The actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge belong to the WP5. In particular, the creation of the project web-platform has been entrusted to a specialized third company.

The research group is presently working on some journal publications, with acknowledgement to the project. The group also presented the project and the ongoing activities during two main international and national conferences:

- the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions, which took place in Parma, 15th -18th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Framework Probabilistico Per La Progettazione Di Soluzioni Di Difesa Costiera E Portuale In Un Contesto Di Cambiamenti Climatici;*
- the National Conference of on Hydraulics and Hydraulic Constructions, which took place in Parma, 15th -18th September 2024, with the following contribution: *L'incertezza Idrodinamica nella Progettazione delle Scogliere Frangiflutti in Massi Naturali;*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which took place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Spatial assessment of the failure probability of rubble-mound breakwaters*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which took place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *On The Uncertainties In Rock-armoured Breakwaters Stability*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which took place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Wave overtopping at vertical walls in shallow water conditions: a predictive formula*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which took place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Vertical seawalls protected by rubble mound structures: prediction tools and physical insight.*
- the 38th International Conference on Coastal Engineering (ICCE2024) which took place in Rome, 8th-14th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Interactions between river and coastal sedimentary balance and effects of hydraulic works on the shoreline changes.*
- the 17th International Coastal Symposium (ICS2024) which took place in Doha, 24th-27th September 2024, with the following contribution: *Analytical solutions for bounded beaches: enhancing coastal management strategies and beach fill project*

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES

With regard to the specific timeframe (bi-monthly/end of project activities), it is below provided:

- a) detailed description of activities carried out by each operational unit with a focus on the timeframe for their implementation

The activities related to Task 1.1, Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 (WP1) have been carried out by all the involved RUs have been completed at the end of the second four-month period. According to the project time schedule, the milestone M1.1 has been achieved and the deliverable D1.1 has been produced.

The activities related to the tasks of WP2 are carried out by UniCT (leader RU) and UniSALENTO. The theoretical basis of the algorithm for the calculation of the failure probability of the system have been defined, and the programming codes for the implantation of Monte Carlo simulations have been drafted by UniCT (Task 2.1). Two performance indexes, namely the ratio between the failure probability of the system and the maximum acceptance limit and the rate of growth of the failure probability, have been defined by UniCT and UniSALENTO (Task 2.2). Moreover, a first attempt to employ such indexes to represent the spatial variability of the defense solution performances has been made in the context of the activities of the Task 2.3, by applying the developed methodology to one of the possible upgrading options for the Catania harbor breakwater.

The activities related to the tasks of WP3 are carried out by UniNA and UniRC. Based on the met-ocean datasets collected in the context of the Task 3.1, which was completed during the second four-month period, hourly wave time series for the Mediterranean Sea were obtained from the Climate Data Store (CDS) (Caires and Yan, 2022) of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) to develop Task 3.2. These wave data sets were generated with the wave forecasting system of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), which uses the spectral wave model WAM (Komen et al., 1994). The ECMWF data were developed to assess the impact of climate change on ocean waves and provide three climate scenarios: a historical reanalysis using ERA5 data (for the period 1976–2017) and two Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) scenarios — RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 — covering the period from 2040 to 2100, as defined by the IPCC. ERA5 is the fifth generation of atmospheric reanalysis of the global climate by ECMWF (Hersbach et al., 2020). To assess the evolution of wave climate over the period 1976–2100 (with a gap from 2017 to 2041 due to the unavailability of CDS-C3S data), key wave parameters such as significant wave height (H_s) and peak period (T_p) were analyzed using statistical methods commonly used in hydrology and meteorology. The presence and significance of trends were assessed using the Mann-Kendall test, a non-parametric method for detecting trends at a certain significance level (e.g. 90%) (Mann, 1945; Kendall, 1962). In addition, the Theil-Sen estimator (Sen, 1968) was used to quantify the increase or decrease of the wave parameters to obtain a robust measure of the magnitude of the trend. The activities of Task 3.3, which consists in the multivariate analysis of wave climate and sea levels, have been started and the preliminary results have been employed for the above-mentioned case study of the Catania harbor breakwater.

The activities related to WP4 have been carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniNA the leader RU. UniNA and UniCT have completed the Task 4.1 during the second four-month

period, providing the basis for the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. The activities related to the Task 4.2 are carried out by UniRC and UniSALENTO, who have performed comparative analysis of failure mechanisms of both conventional and adapted defense solutions, useful to plan the experimental tests and the Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) simulations of the following tasks. The activities related to Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6 are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, RUs are collecting existing experimental and numerical data on damaged and upgraded harbor rubble-mound breakwaters, which includes both structure damage and wave overtopping, vertical wall breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments, considering their own data and available literature data. Moreover, new experimental campaigns have been planned by UniCT (rubble-mound breakwaters), UniRC (vertical breakwaters), UniNA and UniSALENTO (artificial beach nourishment).

The activities related to WP5 are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, Task 5.1 (WP5) is carried out by UniCT and UniSALENTO (leader RU). During this four-month period, the creation of the project web-platform has been entrusted to a specialized third company by UniCT. The activities related to the Task 5.2 are carried out by all the involved RUs. UniCT presented the project PROMETEO during the *European Night of Researches 2024 – Sharper Night 2024* in Catania. UniSALENTO presented the project PROMETEO during the *Convegno Nazionale di Studi Costieri – XV Premio G3 2024* held in Ferrara (Italy). Additionally, based on the experience of the meeting with stakeholders organized in Rome on May 2024, the RUs discussed about the possibility to organize a new dissemination meeting in the next months. Task 5.3 is carried out by all the involved RUs, who are working for the submission of new research works to peer-reviewed journals.

The activities related to Task 6.1, Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 of WP6 are carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniCT the leader RU. The scientific and administrative management of the project (e.g. reporting, coordination, etc.) for technical development and financial monitoring is continuously performed by all the RUs.

- b) description of potential changes to what has been originally approved mentioning the impacts on the aim of the intervention, on the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, on the proposed actions for improvement;

The project activities are proceeding according to the time schedule, and hence no changes to the approved project are planned.

- c) description of potential challenges encountered and of the proposed actions for improvement;

After overcoming the challenges only for the development of the activities related to the task 5.1, i.e. to the creation of the project web-platform, no other difficulties have been experienced until now.

- d) brief description of potential publications.

Based on the preparation of deliverable D1.1 *Report on existing regulations and guidelines for the design of coastal and harbor defense solutions, main existing formulations for the description of failure mechanisms and options for adaptation to climate change*, a joint

publication is under preparation. In the context of the WP4, UniCT will produce a paper on the description of the hydraulic response of rubble-mound breakwaters in terms of wave overtopping, based on both experimental and numerical results. Moreover, UniSALENTO will produce a paper focusing on the characterization of uncertainties in rock armor stability in rubble-mound breakwaters, based on the analysis and synthesis of experimental data available in the literature. UniRC will contribute a paper presenting the structural response of vertical breakwaters consisting of interconnected caissons to transfer shear forces along the structure. The study will incorporate both experimental and numerical data.

Any relevant attached document which includes the abovementioned details

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS

Below the updates on the indicator RRFCI 8 – “*Number of researchers who work in research centres which are recipients of financial support (women; men; non-binary)*” – as per the description in the guidelines included in the n.34 MEF notification from the 17th of October 2022.

Common indicators	Planned value	Implemented value
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (women)	3	3
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (men)	7	7
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (non-binary)	0	0

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS

Below it is provided a description of the forecast scenario on the development of the project, any potential change which is deemed necessary for the future as well as comments on the document.

1) Predictive analysis

The project activities are expected to progress according to the time schedule. In particular, in the next four-monthly UniCT and UniSALENTO will continue to work on the definition of performance and economic indexes and on the application of the probabilistic methodology to case studies. UniNA and UniRC will carry on the activities of WP3 related to the creation of a database of met-ocean data for the Italian coastal areas and to the multivariate analysis of wave climate and sea levels. For the WP4, all the involved RUs will carry on the activities related to the collection of both new and existing experimental and numerical datasets on the performance of rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments. For the WP5, UniCT and UniSALENTO will go on working on the creation of the project web-platform, whereas all the involved RUs will continue to organize meetings with stakeholders and dissemination events, as well as to work on scientific publications. Finally, all the tasks of the WP6 are continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project.

2) Final comments

Currently, the project activities are proceeding as planned during the proposal submission and approval phases. Therefore, no changes to the scheduled activities and/or corrective actions for redefining the stated objectives are anticipated.

The Deputy Rector for Research

(digital signature)

ATTACHMENTS

The below documents are also attached to the technical – scientific report:

Att.1 – Declaration of compliance with DNSH principle and compliance with other principles as per the Environment code;

ROSARIA ESTER
MUSUMECI
14.01.2025
19:40:36
GMT+02:00

5. IV four-month period: December 2024 -
March 2025

FRAMEWORK TECHNICAL -SCIENTIFIC REPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTING ENTITY

PROMETEO - A PRObabilistic fraMEwork for coasTal and harbor dEfense in the cOntext of climate change (prot. P20224T9SK)

 ROSARIA
ESTER
MUSUMECI
17.10.2025
14:47:25
GMT+02:00

NATIONAL RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE PLAN (NRRP) – MISSION 4 COMPONENT 2 INVESTMENT 1.1 – “Fund for the National Research Program and for Projects of National Interest (NRP)”

INTRODUCTION

The Technical-Scientific Report is produced by the *Principal Investigator*, on the basis of a discussion with each local manager for the purposes of collecting data and documenting the progress of each operational unit. It is then submitted according to deadlines envisaged in the related notification.

The Report is composed of the following sections:

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT, where information on the general trends of the projects are included by making reference to the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, to the compliance with the project activities, to the *DNSH* and *Open Access* principles as per the approved project.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES, which entails the description of carried out activities based on the details provided by the operational units involved in the implementation of the project during the collaboration period. It also includes the description of future activities, potential publications and challenges encountered as well as actions for improvement. This, in order to guarantee the achievement of goals that have been established when the financed project was presented.

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS, where EU common indicators connected to the specific investment should be enhanced.

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS, regards the forecast scenario on the development of the project and final comments.

The hereby provided scheme will also be used when presenting the final results of the implemented activities within the project financed by the Ministry.

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT

With regard to the specific timeframe (1st of December 2024 - 31st of March 2025), it is below provided:

- a) a brief summary of the project;

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty of describing their response to wave loads as well as including the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans. In this context, uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. Based on the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations, a probabilistic calculation procedure will be defined for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions, focusing on the Italian situation. The characterization of climate forcing, which will be carried out through a multivariate analysis, will include the combined effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels provided by available projection models. Moreover, current knowledge on the resistance of defense solutions will be improved through the analysis of new and existing experimental and numerical datasets, focusing on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. Finally, easy-to-use performance and economic indexes will be defined to facilitate the use of the project findings by designers and decision-makers. The main expected impacts of PROMETEO are the improvement of current design practices and significant inputs for the revision and the update of the current Italian design guidelines.

The activities are organized in six work packages (hereinafter referred to as WP), each one focused on the objectives reported above. In particular, WP1 builds the foundation of the project based on a critical analysis of the current state of art, whereas WP2 develops the probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions. WP3 and WP4 support WP2, through the statistical treatment of met-ocean data and the experimental and numerical data on failure mechanisms, respectively. The development of web-based practical tools and the dissemination of the project results is carried out in WP5. Finally, coordination, management and monitoring are carried out in

WP6. The results of each WP are organized and presented in deliverables (D), milestones (M) and targets (T), achieved through specific tasks.

b) names of the operational units involved in the implementation of the project;

The research units (RUs) involved in the implementation of the project are:

- Università degli Studi di Catania (UniCT),
- Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (UniNA),
- Università degli Studi "Mediterranea" di Reggio Calabria (UniRC),
- Università del Salento (UniSALENTO).

c) description of the achievement of the objectives connected to the project and related outcomes;

The activities carried out during the fourth four-monthly period regarded:

- Task 2.2 and Task 2.3 of WP2;
- Task 3.2, Task 3.3 of WP3;
- Task 4.1, Task 4.2, Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5 and Task 4.6 of WP4;
- Task 5.1 and Task 5.3 of WP5;
- Task 6.1 and 6.2 of WP6.

WP2

Task 2.2 of WP2 consists in the definition of performance and economic indexes useful to compare different adaptation solutions and climate scenarios, whereas Task 2.3 consists in the application of the probabilistic methodology to case studies. The two tasks directly contribute to the achievement of the specific objectives O2.2 and O2.3, respectively. The ongoing activities will allow to address the milestones M2.1 and M2.2 and the target T2.1, as well as the drafting of the deliverable D2.1.

WP3

Task 3.2 of WP3 consists in the downscaling of such historical and future projection met-ocean datasets collected during the Task 3.1 at sites of interest, whereas Task 3.3 consists in the multivariate analysis of such downscaled data. Both tasks are fundamental for the specific objectives O2.3 and O3.1, namely the validation of the proposed probabilistic methodology through application to emblematic case studies and the probabilistic characterization of hydrodynamic loads acting on harbor and coastal defense solutions based on multivariate analysis, also including the effects of climate change. In particular, the activities carried out so far will contribute to the achievement of the milestones M3.1, M3.2 and M2.2 and the targets T3.1 and T2.1 as well as to the drafting of the deliverables D3.1 and D2.1.

WP4

Task 4.1 of WP4 consists in the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. Task 4.2 of WP4 consists in the comparative analysis of failure mechanisms of rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. In the frame of Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6, it provides useful insight to plan new experimental and numerical activities and to collect existing experimental and numerical datasets on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. The ongoing activities related to these six tasks will contribute to the achievement of the corresponding specific objectives O3.2, O3.3 and O2.3 and of milestones

M4.1, M4.2 and M2.2 and of the targets T4.1 and T2.1, as well as to the drafting of the deliverables D4.1 and D2.1.

WP5

Task 5.1 of WP5 consists in the creation of the web-platform to foster the usability of the project results and improve planning and design practice. The ongoing activities related to these tasks will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.1 and the milestone M5.1. The web-platform itself will represent the deliverable D5.1. Task 5.3 of WP5 consists in the production of scientific publications and in the participation at international or national conferences. The ongoing activities related to this task will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.2, the milestone M5.3 and the targets T5.2 and T5.3.

WP6

Finally, the tasks of WP6 support management and coordination, and hence the corresponding activities, which will be continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project, are fundamental for the achievement of each specific objective of the project. The milestone M6.1 has been completed with the organization of the project kick-off meeting, whereas coordination activities have been carried out to reach the milestone M6.2 at the end of the project. Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 will contain the four-monthly progress reports and the meeting minutes, respectively.

- d) description of the carried out activities which are in compliance with the *DNSH*, *Open Access* principles as well as with *gender*, *generational* principles and with those of *Equal opportunities*

The activities carried out during the fourth four-monthly period consisted in:

- the definition of performance indexes;
- the application of the probabilistic framework to case studies;
- the downscaling of existing met-ocean datasets;
- the multivariate analysis of met-ocean datasets;
- the definition of analysis procedures;
- the performance of experimental and numerical tests;
- the creation of the project web-platform.

All these activities do not require interactions with the environment, and hence they are in compliance with the DNSH principle, since they do not affect the six environmental objectives indicated by the in art. 17 of the EU regulation 2020/852 in any way. In this regard, it should be noted that the final results of the project will contribute to the achievement of the second environmental objective, namely the adaptation to climate change. The Open Access principles are also observed, particularly referring to the development of the project web-platform and to the consequent free availability of the project data and results, as well as to the planned production of open-access scientific papers. The respect of the gender and generational and of equal opportunities principles is ensured by the varied composition of project team. In particular, despite coastal engineering is a traditional male working environment, the project team includes also female researchers, among which the Principal Investigator and the Substitute Principal Investigator of the project. Moreover, both male and female young researchers participate to the project activities under the guidance of the senior members of the group.

- e) description of the actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge

The actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge belong to the WP5. In particular, the creation of the project web-platform has been entrusted to a specialized third company and a first version of its template has already been produced.

The research group is constantly working on some journal publications, with acknowledgement to the project. The following papers have been already published on peer-reviewed journals:

- Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., & Saponieri, A. (2024). Laboratory investigation on pore pressures inside a rubble mound breakwater in depth-limited waters. *Applied Ocean Research*, 147, 103988.
- Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Leone, E., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., ... & Saponieri, A. (2025). The influence of shallow water on rock armour stability. *Coastal Engineering*, 197, 104657 (Open Access).

The group also presented the project and the ongoing activities during two main international and national conferences:

- the AIOM meeting 2025, which took place in Catania, 30th-31st January 2025, with the following contribution: *Valutazione della distribuzione spaziale delle performance di frangiflutti a gettata adeguati*;
- 41st IAHR2025 Word Congress – Singapore, 22-27 June 2025, with the following contribution Numerical modelling of surf zone hydrodynamics using SWASH (accepted as oral presentation);
- 11st SCACR2025 – Dubrovnik, 24-26 September 2025, with the following contribution Influence of spectral cut-off frequency on armour stability in shallow water (accepted as oral presentation).

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES

With regard to the specific timeframe (bi-monthly/end of project activities), it is below provided:

- a) detailed description of activities carried out by each operational unit with a focus on the timeframe for their implementation

The activities related to Task 1.1, Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 (WP1) have been carried out by all the involved RUs have been completed at the end of the second four-month period. According to the project time schedule, the milestone M1.1 has been achieved and the deliverable D1.1 has been produced.

The activities related to the tasks of WP2 are carried out by UniCT (leader RU) and UniSALENTO. The theoretical basis of the algorithm for the calculation of the failure probability of the system have been defined, and the programming codes for the implantation of Monte Carlo simulations have been drafted by UniCT during the previous four-month period (Task 2.1). In the context of task 2.2, two performance indexes, namely the ratio between the failure probability of the system and the maximum acceptance limit and the rate of growth of the failure probability, have been defined by UniCT and UniSALENTO. Moreover, the two RUs are working on the definition of one or more economic indexes, which could integrate the information provided by the performance indexes. A first attempt to employ the performance indexes to represent the spatial variability of the defense solution performances has been made in the context of the activities of the Task 2.3 during the third four-month period, by applying the developed methodology to one of the possible upgrading options for the Catania harbor breakwater. In addition to this, during the fourths four-month period UniSALENTO has prepared the data needed for the application of the probabilistic framework to a second Italian case study.

The activities related to the tasks of WP3 are carried out by UniNA and UniRC. Based on the met-ocean datasets collected in the context of the Task 3.1, which was completed during the second four-month period, hourly wave time series for the Mediterranean Sea were obtained from the Climate Data Store (CDS) (Caires and Yan, 2022) of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) to develop Task 3.2. During the third four-month period, key wave parameters such as significant wave height (H_s) and peak period (T_p) were analyzed using statistical methods commonly used in hydrology and meteorology. As regards the activities of Task 3.3, historical time series from various databases were analyzed, extrapolating the extreme values of: wave height, mean period, peak period, and direction, along all Italian coasts. The same analysis was performed on forecasted time series, which provide estimates of future met-ocean climate for the period 2041–2100, taking into account different emission scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5), including factors such as sea level rise, greenhouse gas concentrations, and changes in atmospheric and oceanic circulation patterns. Sites of interest were selected for the main Italian seas, following a procedure aimed at identifying the most engineering-relevant extreme events. For these sites, a probabilistic analysis was carried out using both historical and forecasted datasets, allowing for the estimation of design waves. After a detailed reconstruction of the bathymetries, the design waves were propagated near coast using the SWAN model, obtaining the extreme nearshore storm surge events.

The activities related to WP4 have been carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniNA the leader RU. UniNA and UniCT have completed the Task 4.1 during the second four-month

period, providing the basis for the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. The activities related to the Task 4.2, carried out by UniRC and UniSALENTO, were completed during the third four-month period. The activities related to Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6 are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, RUs are collecting existing experimental and numerical data on damaged and upgraded harbor rubble-mound breakwaters, which includes both structure damage and wave overtopping, vertical wall breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments, considering their own data and available literature data. Moreover, new experimental and numerical campaigns have been planned by UniCT (rubble-mound breakwaters), UniRC (vertical breakwaters), UniNA and UniSALENTO (artificial beach nourishment). UniSALENTO and UniNA are testing the effects of a beach nourishment in front of a vertical wall on wave/structure interaction processes, with particular reference to the overtopping phenomenon. Different grain size and geometry of the nourishment are being tested numerically using XBeach.

The activities related to WP5 are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, Task 5.1 (WP5) is carried out by UniCT and UniSALENTO (leader RU). During the fourth four-month period, the first version of the project web-platform template has been created by a specialized third company by UniCT. All the involved RUs have worked on the definition of the web-platform contents. Task 5.3 is carried out by all the involved RUs, who have attended to the national AIOM meeting 2025 and are currently working for the submission of new research works to peer-reviewed journals, in addition to the papers already published.

The activities related to Task 6.1, Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 of WP6 are carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniCT the leader RU. The scientific and administrative management of the project (e.g. reporting, coordination, etc.) for technical development and financial monitoring is continuously performed by all the RUs.

- b) description of potential changes to what has been originally approved mentioning the impacts on the aim of the intervention, on the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, on the proposed actions for improvement;

The project activities are proceeding according to the time schedule, and hence no changes to the approved project are planned.

- c) description of potential challenges encountered and of the proposed actions for improvement;

During the execution of the project activities, new information and data concerning Task 3.2 of WP3 and Task 4.1 and Task 4.2 of WP4 have been found. As a consequence of that, although it was not foreseen in the time schedule, the RUs decided to integrate the results of the above-mentioned tasks.

- d) brief description of potential publications.

In the context of the WP4, UniCT will produce a paper on the description of the hydraulic response of rubble-mound breakwaters in terms of wave overtopping, based on both experimental and numerical results. UniSalento will produce a paper on the primary sources of uncertainty in the hydraulic stability of rock-armored rubble mound breakwaters, based on 2D experimental datasets collected from literature. UniRC will contribute a paper presenting the structural response of vertical breakwaters consisting of interconnected caissons to

transfer shear forces along the structure. The study will incorporate both experimental and numerical data. Furthermore, UNIRC is about to publish a study that assesses the uncertainties related to climate change. Wave parameters along the Italian coasts were analyzed using data from various databases, including historical data and future projections. A downscaling model was used to adapt offshore data to realistic nearshore conditions, with the aim of comparing the results derived from historical and projected series and improving long-term risk assessments.

Any relevant attached document which includes the abovementioned details

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS

Below the updates on the indicator RRFCI 8 – “*Number of researchers who work in research centres which are recipients of financial support (women; men; non-binary)*” – as per the description in the guidelines included in the n.34 MEF notification from the 17th of October 2022.

Common indicators	Planned value	Implemented value
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (women)	3	3
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (men)	7	7
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (non-binary)	0	0

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS

Below it is provided a description of the forecast scenario on the development of the project, any potential change which is deemed necessary for the future as well as comments on the document.

1) Predictive analysis

The project activities are expected to progress according to the time schedule. In particular, in the next four-monthly UniCT and UniSALENTO will continue to work on the definition of economic indexes and on the application of the probabilistic methodology to case studies. UniNA and UniRC will carry on the activities of WP3 related to the creation of a database of met-ocean data for the Italian coastal areas and to the multivariate analysis of wave climate and sea levels. For the WP4, all the involved RUs will carry on the activities related to the collection of both new and existing experimental and numerical datasets on the performance of rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments. For the WP5, UniCT and UniSALENTO will go on working on the creation of the project web-platform, whereas all the involved RUs will continue to organize meetings with stakeholders and dissemination events, as well as to work on scientific publications. Finally, all the tasks of the WP6 are continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project.

2) Final comments

Currently, the project activities are proceeding as planned during the proposal submission and approval phases. Therefore, no changes to the scheduled activities and/or corrective actions for redefining the stated objectives are anticipated.

Legal Representative

Prof. Enrico Foti

(digital signature)

ATTACHMENTS

The below documents are also attached to the technical – scientific report:

Att.1 – Declaration of compliance with DNSH principle and compliance with other principles as per the Environment code;

6. V four-month period: April 2025 - July 2025

FRAMEWORK TECHNICAL -SCIENTIFIC REPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTING ENTITY

PROMETEO - A PRObabilistic fraMEwork for coasTal and harbor dEfense in the cOntext of climate change (prot. P20224T9SK)

NATIONAL RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE PLAN (NRRP) – MISSION 4 COMPONENT 2 INVESTMENT 1.1 – “Fund for the National Research Program and for Projects of National Interest (NRP)”

INTRODUCTION

The Technical-Scientific Report is produced by the *Principal Investigator*, on the basis of a discussion with each local manager for the purposes of collecting data and documenting the progress of each operational unit. It is then submitted according to deadlines envisaged in the related notification.

The Report is composed of the following sections:

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT, where information on the general trends of the projects are included by making reference to the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, to the compliance with the project activities, to the *DNSH* and *Open Access* principles as per the approved project.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES, which entails the description of carried out activities based on the details provided by the operational units involved in the implementation of the project during the collaboration period. It also includes the description of future activities, potential publications and challenges encountered as well as actions for improvement. This, in order to guarantee the achievement of goals that have been established when the financed project was presented.

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS, where EU common indicators connected to the specific investment should be enhanced.

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS, regards the forecast scenario on the development of the project and final comments.

The hereby provided scheme will also be used when presenting the final results of the implemented activities within the project financed by the Ministry.

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT

With regard to the specific timeframe (1st of April 2025 - 31st of July 2025), it is below provided:

- a) a brief summary of the project;

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty of describing their response to wave loads as well as including the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans. In this context, uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. Based on the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations, a probabilistic calculation procedure will be defined for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions, focusing on the Italian situation. The characterization of climate forcing, which will be carried out through a multivariate analysis, will include the combined effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels provided by available projection models. Moreover, current knowledge on the resistance of defense solutions will be improved through the analysis of new and existing experimental and numerical datasets, focusing on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. Finally, easy-to-use performance and economic indexes will be defined to facilitate the use of the project findings by designers and decision-makers. The main expected impacts of PROMETEO are the improvement of current design practices and significant inputs for the revision and the update of the current Italian design guidelines.

The activities are organized in six work packages (hereinafter referred to as WP), each one focused on the objectives reported above. In particular, WP1 builds the foundation of the project based on a critical analysis of the current state of art, whereas WP2 develops the probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions. WP3 and WP4 support WP2, through the statistical treatment of met-ocean data and the experimental and numerical data on failure mechanisms, respectively. The development of web-based practical tools and the dissemination of the project results is carried out in WP5. Finally, coordination, management and monitoring are carried out in

WP6. The results of each WP are organized and presented in deliverables (D), milestones (M) and targets (T), achieved through specific tasks.

b) names of the operational units involved in the implementation of the project;

The research units (RUs) involved in the implementation of the project are:

- Università degli Studi di Catania (UniCT),
- Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (UniNA),
- Università degli Studi "Mediterranea" di Reggio Calabria (UniRC),
- Università del Salento (UniSALENTO).

c) description of the achievement of the objectives connected to the project and related outcomes;

The activities carried out during the fifth four-monthly period regarded:

- Task 2.2 and Task 2.3 of WP2;
- Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 of WP3;
- Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5 and Task 4.6 of WP4;
- Task 5.1 and Task 5.3 of WP5;
- Task 6.1 and 6.2 of WP6.

WP2

Task 2.2 of WP2 consists in the definition of performance and economic indexes useful to compare different adaptation solutions and climate scenarios, whereas Task 2.3 consists in the application of the probabilistic methodology to case studies. The two tasks directly contribute to the achievement of the specific objectives O2.2 and O2.3, respectively. The ongoing activities will allow to address the milestones M2.1 and M2.2 and the target T2.1, as well as the drafting of the deliverable D2.1.

WP3

Task 3.2 of WP3 consists in the downscaling of such historical and future projection met-ocean datasets collected during the Task 3.1 at sites of interest, whereas Task 3.3 consists in the multivariate analysis of such downscaled data. Both tasks are fundamental for the specific objectives O2.3 and O3.1, namely the validation of the proposed probabilistic methodology through application to emblematic case studies and the probabilistic characterization of hydrodynamic loads acting on harbor and coastal defense solutions based on multivariate analysis, also including the effects of climate change. In particular, the activities carried out so far will contribute to the achievement of the milestones M3.1, M3.2 and M2.2 and the targets T3.1 and T2.1 as well as to the drafting of the deliverables D3.1 and D2.1.

WP4

The ongoing activities related to Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6 will contribute to the achievement of the corresponding specific objectives O3.2, O3.3 and O2.3 and of milestones M4.1, M4.2 and M2.2 and of the targets T4.1 and T2.1, as well as to the drafting of the deliverables D4.1 and D2.1.

WP5

Task 5.1 of WP5 consists in the creation of the web-platform to foster the usability of the project results and improve planning and design practice. The ongoing activities related to these tasks will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.1 and the milestone M5.1. The web-platform itself will represent the deliverable D5.1. Task 5.3 of WP5 consists in the production of scientific publications and in the participation at international or national

conferences. The ongoing activities related to this task will contribute to the achievement of the specific objective O4.2, the milestone M5.3 and the targets T5.2 and T5.3.

WP6

Finally, the tasks of WP6 support management and coordination, and hence the corresponding activities, which will be continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project, are fundamental for the achievement of each specific objective of the project. The milestone M6.1 has been completed with the organization of the project kick-off meeting, whereas coordination activities have been carried out to reach the milestone M6.2 at the end of the project. Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 will contain the four-monthly progress reports and the meeting minutes, respectively.

- d) description of the carried out activities which are in compliance with the *DNSH*, *Open Access* principles as well as with *gender*, *generational* principles and with those of *Equal opportunities*

The activities carried out during the fifth four-monthly period consisted in:

- the definition of performance indexes;
- the application of the probabilistic framework to case studies;
- the downscaling of existing met-ocean datasets;
- the multivariate analysis of met-ocean datasets;
- the performance of experimental and numerical tests and the collection of existing datasets;
- the creation of the project web-platform.

All these activities do not require interactions with the environment, and hence they are in compliance with the DNSH principle, since they do not affect the six environmental objectives indicated by the in art. 17 of the EU regulation 2020/852 in any way. In this regard, it should be noted that the final results of the project will contribute to the achievement of the second environmental objective, namely the adaptation to climate change. The Open Access principles are also observed, particularly referring to the development of the project web-platform and to the consequent free availability of the project data and results, as well as to the planned production of open-access scientific papers. The respect of the gender and generational and of equal opportunities principles is ensured by the varied composition of project team. In particular, despite coastal engineering is a traditional male working environment, the project team includes also female researchers, among which the Principal Investigator and the Substitute Principal Investigator of the project. Moreover, both male and female young researchers participate to the project activities under the guidance of the senior members of the group.

- e) description of the actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge

The actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge belong to the WP5. In particular, the creation of the project web-platform has been entrusted to a specialized third company and it has been launched on May 2025.

The research group is constantly working on some journal publications, with acknowledgement to the project. The following papers have been already published on peer-reviewed journals:

- Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., & Saponieri, A. (2024). Laboratory investigation on pore pressures inside a rubble mound breakwater in depth-limited waters. *Applied Ocean Research*, 147, 103988.
- Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Leone, E., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., ... & Saponieri, A. (2025). The influence of shallow water on rock armour stability. *Coastal Engineering*, 197, 104657 (Open Access).
- Scaravaglione, G., Melby, J. A., Tomasicchio, G. R., van Gent, M. R., & Saponieri, A. (2025). On the uncertainties in stone armor stability. *Coastal Engineering*, 202, 104790.

The group also presented the project and the ongoing activities during international and national conferences:

- the AIOM meeting 2025, which took place in Catania, 30th-31st January 2025, with the following contribution: *Valutazione della distribuzione spaziale delle performance di frangiflutti a gettata adeguati*;
- 41st IAHR2025 Word Congress – Singapore, 22-27 June 2025, with the following contribution Numerical modelling of surf zone hydrodynamics using SWASH;
- 11st SCACR2025 – Dubrovnik, 24-26 September 2025, with the following contribution Influence of spectral cut-off frequency on armour stability in shallow water (accepted as oral presentation).
- 7th Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (EMCEI-2025) – Reggio Calabria, 23-26 June 2025, with the following contribution: *A Data-Driven Approach Considering Climate Change to Design Coastal and Port Defense Structures*.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES

With regard to the specific timeframe (bi-monthly/end of project activities), it is below provided:

- a) detailed description of activities carried out by each operational unit with a focus on the timeframe for their implementation

The activities related to Task 1.1, Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 (WP1) have been carried out by all the involved RUs have been completed at the end of the second four-month period. According to the project time schedule, the milestone M1.1 has been achieved and the deliverable D1.1 has been produced.

The activities related to the tasks of WP2 are carried out by UniCT (leader RU) and UniSALENTO. The theoretical basis of the algorithm for the calculation of the failure probability of the system have been defined, and the programming codes for the implantation of Monte Carlo simulations have been drafted by UniCT during the previous four-month period (Task 2.1). Moreover, in the context of Task 2.2, two performance indexes, namely the ratio between the failure probability of the system and the maximum acceptance limit and the rate of growth of the failure probability, have been defined by UniCT and UniSALENTO. The activities of the fifth four-month period focused on the definition of one or more economic indexes, which could integrate the information provided by the performance indexes. A first attempt to employ the performance indexes to represent the spatial variability of the defense solution performances has been made in the context of the activities of the Task 2.3 during the third four-month period, by applying the developed methodology to one of the possible upgrading options for the Catania harbor breakwater. In addition to this, during the fourth and fifth four-month periods UniSALENTO and UniCT have started the application of the probabilistic method to two new Italian case studies, namely the harbor rubble-mound breakwater of Arenella and the harbor vertical breakwater of Vado Ligure, which together with the case of the Port of Catania represent the three Italian case studies required to achieve the target T2.

The activities related to the tasks of WP3 are carried out by UniNA and UniRC. During the fifth four-month period, in the context of the Task 3.3, UniRC carried out a comparative analysis in order to assess the potential influence of the selected wave dataset on the design and associated costs of coastal protection structures, a comparative analysis was carried out. A vertical breakwater was considered as a reference case, and the structural elements were dimensioned according to standard design guidelines. The resulting costs were then estimated. The analysis highlighted notable differences in cost estimates depending on the dataset used. Furthermore, the comparison between current and projected future wave conditions revealed significant variations, underlining the importance of dataset selection in long-term planning. UniNA discussed the uncertainties related to the commonly adopted procedures for inferring extreme wave conditions. These uncertainties can arise from the wave datasets used (e.g. RON wave buoy measurements or numerical data from MEDSEA or ERA5) and the theoretical framework employed during the analysis. Finally, the use of semi-parametric and non-parametric methods to describe extreme waves have been proposed.

The activities related to WP4 have been carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniNA the leader RU. UniNA and UniCT have completed the Task 4.1 during the second four-month period, providing the basis for the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the

deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. The activities related to the Task 4.2, carried out by UniRC and UniSALENTO, were completed during the third four-month period. The activities related to Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6 are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, RUs are collecting existing experimental and numerical data on damaged and upgraded harbor rubble-mound breakwaters, which includes both structure damage and wave overtopping, vertical wall breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments, considering their own data and available literature data. Moreover, UniCT is conducting new experimental tests on upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters, in order to extend the existing dataset on this kind of structure. UniSALENTO and UniNA continuing to test the effects of a beach nourishment in front of a vertical wall on wave/structure interaction processes, with particular reference to the overtopping phenomenon. Different grain size and geometry of the nourishment are being tested numerically using XBeach. Moreover, UniNA is examining the capability of some adaptive solutions in reducing wave overtopping. In particular, the physical experiments concern vertical wall protected by rubble mound breakwaters combined with Reef Ball modules seated onto the crown.

The activities related to WP5 are carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, Task 5.1 (WP5) is carried out by UniCT and UniSALENTO (leader RU). During the fifth four-month period, the project web-platform, created by a specialized third company under the supervision of UniCT, has been launched. All the involved RUs are working on the definition of the web-platform contents. Task 5.3 is carried out by all the involved RUs. Indeed, UniSALENTO attended to the 41st IAHR2025 Word Congress in Singapore. UniRC participated in the 7th Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (EMCEI-2025) in Reggio Calabria. Moreover, all the RUs are currently working for the submission of new research works to peer-reviewed journals, among which a joint paper based on the contents of the deliverable D1.1. UniSALENTO is currently working on a review journal paper entitled “A comprehensive review of the primary sources of uncertainty in stone armor stability” to be submitted before the end of July on Coastal Engineering.

The activities related to Task 6.1, Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 of WP6 are carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniCT the leader RU. The scientific and administrative management of the project (e.g. reporting, coordination, etc.) for technical development and financial monitoring is continuously performed by all the RUs.

- b) description of potential changes to what has been originally approved mentioning the impacts on the aim of the intervention, on the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, on the proposed actions for improvement;

Considering the extension of the Project deadline from 30th of November 2025 to the 28th of February 2026 (*see D.D. no. 1409 of the 14th of September 2022 - DECRETO DI PROROGA per la conclusione delle attività progettuali al 28 febbraio 2026*), the time schedule has been modified to allow the partners to deepen the ongoing analyses and to reinforce further cooperation among research units for joint work and publications, within a longer timeframe. In particular, the following changes have been made:

- WP2: tasks 2.2 and 2.3, and consequently the milestones M2.1 and M2.2, the deliverable D2.1 and the target T2.1, will be completed by February 2026;
- WP3: task 3.3, and consequently the milestone M3.2, the deliverable D3.1 and the target T3.1, will be completed by January 2026;
- WP4: tasks 4.3, 4.4, 4.5 and 4.6, and consequently the milestone M4.2, the deliverable D4.1 and the target T4.1, will be completed by January 2026;

- WP5: tasks 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, and consequently the milestones M5.1, M5.2 and M5.3, the deliverables D5.1 and D5.2 and the targets T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3, will be completed by February 2026;
- WP6: tasks 6.1 and 6.2, and consequently the milestones M6.1 and M6.2, the deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 and the target T6.1, will be completed by February 2026.

c) description of potential challenges encountered and of the proposed actions for improvement;

During the execution of the project activities, new information and data concerning Task 3.2 of WP3 have been found. As a consequence of that, although it was not foreseen in the time schedule, the RUs decided to integrate the results of the above-mentioned task.

d) brief description of potential publications.

In the context of the WP4, UniCT will produce a paper on the description of the hydraulic response of rubble-mound breakwaters in terms of wave overtopping, based on both experimental and numerical results. UniSalento will produce a review paper on the primary sources of uncertainty in stone armor stability, based on semi-quantitative contribution of each source and sub-class to the total uncertainty based on the body of knowledge from the literature and data analysis. UniRC will contribute a paper presenting the structural response of vertical breakwaters consisting of interconnected caissons to transfer shear forces along the structure. The study will incorporate both experimental and numerical data. Furthermore, UNIRC is about to publish a study that assesses the uncertainties related to climate change. Wave parameters along the Italian coasts were analyzed using data from various databases, including historical data and future projections. A downscaling model was used to adapt offshore data to realistic nearshore conditions, with the aim of comparing the results derived from historical and projected series and improving long-term risk assessments. Another potential publication mainly based on the activities carried out by UniRC will focus on the comparison between different wave datasets and the impact their selection may have on the design of vertical breakwaters. The objective is to highlight how variations in input data can significantly influence key design parameters and associated construction costs, thus underlining the importance of accurate dataset selection in coastal engineering applications. UniNA is working on a potential publication dealing with the role of some adaptive solutions, such as seawalls protected by nourishment or rubble mound structures, in reducing the flooding risk of coastal areas.

Finally, all the RUs are started to work to a joint paper based on the contents of the deliverable D1.1.

Any relevant attached document which includes the abovementioned details

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS

Below the updates on the indicator RRFCI 8 – “*Number of researchers who work in research centres which are recipients of financial support (women; men; non-binary)*” – as per the description in the guidelines included in the n.34 MEF notification from the 17th of October 2022.

Common indicators	Planned value	Implemented value
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (women)	3	3
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (men)	7	7
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (non-binary)	0	0

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS

Below it is provided a description of the forecast scenario on the development of the project, any potential change which is deemed necessary for the future as well as comments on the document.

1) Predictive analysis

The project activities are expected to progress according to the time schedule updated considering the new Project deadline (i.e. February 2026). In particular, in the next four-monthly UniCT and UniSALENTO will continue to work on the definition of economic indexes and on the application of the probabilistic methodology to case studies. UniNA and UniRC will carry on the activities of WP3 related to the multivariate analysis of wave climate and sea levels. For the WP4, all the involved RUs will carry on the activities related to the collection of both new and existing experimental and numerical datasets on the performance of rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments. For the WP5, UniCT and UniSALENTO will go on working on the update of the contents of the project web-platform, supported by UniNA and UniRC. Moreover, all the involved RUs will work on the organization of at least one final meeting with stakeholders and dissemination events, as well as on the drafting of scientific publications. Finally, all the tasks of the WP6 are continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project.

2) Final comments

The time schedule of the Project activities has been updated considering the new final deadline of the 28th of February 2026. Indeed, although the project activities are proceeding as planned, the time schedule has been extended to allow the partners to deepen the ongoing analyses and to reinforce further cooperation among research units for joint work and publications, within a longer timeframe. No further changes to the scheduled activities and/or corrective actions for redefining the stated objectives are anticipated.

The Legal Rappresentative

(digital signature)

ATTACHMENTS

The below documents are also attached to the technical – scientific report:

Att.1 – Declaration of compliance with DNSH principle and compliance with other principles as per the Environment code;

7. VI period: August 2025 – February 2026

FRAMEWORK TECHNICAL -SCIENTIFIC REPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTING ENTITY

PROMETEO - A PRObabilistic fraMEwork for coasTal and harbor dEfense in the cOntext of climate change (prot. P20224T9SK)

NATIONAL RECOVERY AND RESILIENCE PLAN (NRRP) – MISSION 4 COMPONENT 2 INVESTMENT 1.1 – “Fund for the National Research Program and for Projects of National Interest (NRP)”

INTRODUCTION

The Technical-Scientific Report is produced by the *Principal Investigator*, on the basis of a discussion with each local manager for the purposes of collecting data and documenting the progress of each operational unit. It is then submitted according to deadlines envisaged in the related notification.

The Report is composed of the following sections:

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT, where information on the general trends of the projects are included by making reference to the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, to the compliance with the project activities, to the *DNSH* and *Open Access* principles as per the approved project.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES, which entails the description of carried out activities based on the details provided by the operational units involved in the implementation of the project during the collaboration period. It also includes the description of future activities, potential publications and challenges encountered as well as actions for improvement. This, in order to guarantee the achievement of goals that have been established when the financed project was presented.

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS, where EU common indicators connected to the specific investment should be enhanced.

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS, regards the forecast scenario on the development of the project and final comments.

The hereby provided scheme will also be used when presenting the final results of the implemented activities within the project financed by the Ministry.

SECTION 1 – GENERAL TRENDS OF THE PROJECT

With regard to the specific timeframe (1st of August 2025 – 28th of February 2026), it is below provided:

- a) a brief summary of the project;

Coastal zones host many natural ecosystems and economic and social activities, which require protection from the action of the sea. The design of coastal and harbor defense solutions is a complex task, due to the difficulty of describing their response to wave loads as well as including the stochastic nature of climate forcing. Nowadays, the existence of a huge number of aging defense structures and climate change-induced forcing variability highlight the need for sustainable maintenance and adaptation plans. In this context, uncertainties related to the non-conventional nature of historical or adapted structures and to the effects of climate change on marine climate must be properly considered during the design process. Traditional deterministic design methodologies do not take into account such uncertainties, whereas probabilistic design methods employ probability distribution functions of the involved variables to estimate the failure probability of a certain system. In the world, only a few national design guidelines started to use probabilistic approaches, which however refer just to newly built structures, while the effects of climate change are considered only in a simplified manner. In Italy, technical recommendations for maritime dikes and coastal defense solutions date back to the '90s and are still based on a deterministic approach. Moreover, though climate-aware engineering design is required, for example by EU guidelines for public work funding, no solid know-how is available to designers and decision-makers.

In this context, PROMETEO aims to foster a more resilient approach for the management of coastal areas, by developing a probabilistic design framework able to consider the uncertainties related to the response of new, existing or adapted coastal and harbor defense solutions and met-ocean forcing in a changing climate. Based on the information derived from the critical review of existing design regulations, a probabilistic calculation procedure will be defined for the assessment of the performances of defense interventions, focusing on the Italian situation. The characterization of climate forcing, which will be carried out through a multivariate analysis, will include the combined effects of climate change on wave climate and sea levels provided by available projection models. Moreover, current knowledge on the resistance of defense solutions will be improved through the analysis of new and existing experimental and numerical datasets, focusing on rubble-mound and vertical breakwaters, seawalls and artificial beach nourishments. Finally, easy-to-use performance and economic indexes will be defined to facilitate the use of the project findings by designers and decision-makers. The main expected impacts of PROMETEO are the improvement of current design practices and significant inputs for the revision and the update of the current Italian design guidelines.

The activities are organized in six work packages (hereinafter referred to as WP), each one focused on the objectives reported above. In particular, WP1 builds the foundation of the project based on a critical analysis of the current state of art, whereas WP2 develops the probabilistic framework for the assessment of the performances of coastal and harbor defense solutions. WP3 and WP4 support WP2, through the statistical treatment of met-ocean data and the experimental and numerical data on failure mechanisms, respectively. The development of web-based practical tools and the dissemination of the project results is carried out in WP5. Finally, coordination, management and monitoring are carried out in

WP6. The results of each WP are organized and presented in deliverables (D), milestones (M) and targets (T), achieved through specific tasks.

b) names of the operational units involved in the implementation of the project;

The research units (RUs) involved in the implementation of the project are:

- Università degli Studi di Catania (UniCT),
- Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II (UniNA),
- Università degli Studi "Mediterranea" di Reggio Calabria (UniRC),
- Università del Salento (UniSALENTO).

c) description of the achievement of the objectives connected to the project and related outcomes;

The activities carried out during the sixth four-monthly period regarded:

- Task 2.2 and Task 2.3 of WP2;
- Task 3.2 and Task 3.3 of WP3;
- Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5 and Task 4.6 of WP4;
- Task 5.1, Task 5.2 and Task 5.3 of WP5;
- Task 6.1 and 6.2 of WP6.

WP2

Task 2.2 of WP2 consists in the definition of performance and economic indexes useful to compare different adaptation solutions and climate scenarios, whereas Task 2.3 consists in the application of the probabilistic methodology to case studies. The two tasks directly contributed to the achievement of the specific objectives O2.2 and O2.3, respectively. The activities allowed to address the milestones M2.1 and M2.2 and the target T2.1, as well as the drafting of the deliverable D2.1.

WP3

Task 3.2 of WP3 consists in the downscaling of such historical and future projection met-ocean datasets collected during the Task 3.1 at sites of interest, whereas Task 3.3 of WP3 consists in the multivariate analysis of such downscaled data. Both tasks are fundamental for the specific objectives O2.3 and O3.1, namely the validation of the proposed probabilistic methodology through application to emblematic case studies and the probabilistic characterization of hydrodynamic loads acting on harbor and coastal defense solutions based on multivariate analysis, also including the effects of climate change. In particular, the activities carried out contributed to the achievement of the milestones M3.2 and M2.2 and the targets T3.1 and T2.1 as well as to the writing of the deliverables D3.1 and D2.1.

WP4

The activities related to Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6 contributed to the achievement of the corresponding specific objectives O3.2, O3.3 and O2.3 and of milestones M4.1, M4.2 and M2.2 and of the targets T4.1 and T2.1, as well as to the finalization of the deliverables D4.1 and D2.1.

WP5

Task 5.1 of WP5 consists in the creation of the web-platform to foster the usability of the project results and improve planning and design practice. The activities related to these tasks contributed to the achievement of the specific objective O4.1 and the milestone M5.1. The web-platform itself represents the deliverable D5.1. Task 5.2 consists of the organization of workshops, meetings with relevant stakeholders and dissemination events. The activities

related to this task contributed to the achievement of the specific objective O4.2, the milestone M5.2, and the target T5.1, as well as to the deliverable D5.2. Task 5.3 of WP5 consists in the production of scientific publications and in participation at international or national conferences. The activities related to this task contributed to the achievement of the specific objective O4.2, the milestone M5.3 and the targets T5.2 and T5.3.

WP6

Finally, the tasks of WP6 support management and coordination, and hence the corresponding activities, which were continuously carried out for the whole duration of the project, were fundamental for the achievement of each specific objective of the project. The milestone M6.1 was completed with the organization of the project kick-off meeting, whereas coordination activities were carried out to reach the milestone M6.2 at the end of the project. Deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 contain the four-monthly progress reports and the meeting minutes, respectively. In particular, the final meeting with stakeholders was organized in Naples on the 26th of February 2026.

- d) description of the activities carried out which are in compliance with the *DNSH*, *Open Access* principles as well as with *gender*, *generational* principles and with those of *Equal opportunities*

The activities carried out during the sixth four-monthly period consisted in:

- the definition of economic indexes;
- the application of the probabilistic framework to case studies;
- the downscaling of existing met-ocean datasets;
- the multivariate analysis of met-ocean datasets;
- the performance of experimental and numerical tests and the collection of existing datasets;
- the preparation of material for the project web-platform;
- the organization of the second meeting with stakeholders (final conference);
- the organization of a special issue, the drafting of scientific papers to be submitted to peer-reviewed journals and/or presented at international conferences.

All these activities do not require interactions with the environment, and hence they are in compliance with the *DNSH* principle, since they do not affect the six environmental objectives indicated by the in art. 17 of the EU regulation 2020/852 in any way. In this regard, it should be noted that the final results of the project will contribute to the achievement of the second environmental objective, namely the adaptation to climate change. The *Open Access* principles are also observed, particularly referring to the development of the project web-platform and to the consequent free availability of the project data and results, as well as to the planned production of open-access scientific papers. The respect of the *gender* and *generational* and of *equal opportunities* principles is ensured by the varied composition of project team. In particular, despite coastal engineering is a traditional male working environment, the project team includes also female researchers, among which the Principal Investigator and the Substitute Principal Investigator of the project. Moreover, both male and female young researchers participate to the project activities under the guidance of the senior members of the group.

- e) description of the actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge

The actions aimed at informing and disseminating knowledge belong to the WP5. In particular, the project web-platform launched on May 2025 has been reviewed and new materials are currently being prepared for upload.

The research group is constantly working on some journal publications, with acknowledgement to the project. The following papers have been already published on peer-reviewed journals or are under revision:

- Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., & Saponieri, A. (2024). Laboratory investigation on pore pressures inside a rubble mound breakwater in depth-limited waters. *Applied Ocean Research*, 147, 103988.
- Scaravaglione, G., Marino, S., Francone, A., Leone, E., Damiani, L., Tomasicchio, G. R., ... & Saponieri, A. (2025). The influence of shallow water on rock armour stability. *Coastal Engineering*, 197, 104657 (Open Access).
- Scaravaglione, G., Melby, J. A., Tomasicchio, G. R., van Gent, M. R., & Saponieri, A. (2025). On the uncertainties in stone armor stability. *Coastal Engineering*, 202, 104790.
- Scaravaglione, G., & Melby, J. A. (2026). A comprehensive review of the primary sources of uncertainty in stone armor stability. *Coastal Engineering*, 205, 104930.
- Stagnitti, M., Esposito, A., Simonetti, I., Foti, E., Musumeci, R.E., Cappietti, L. (2026) Wave overtopping of upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters: blind comparison between experimental and numerical data. *Ocean Engineering (in print)*.

The group also presented the project and the ongoing activities during international and national conferences:

- the AIOM meeting 2025, which took place in Catania, 30th-31st January 2025, with the following contribution: *Valutazione della distribuzione spaziale delle performance di frangiflutti a gettata adeguati*;
- 41st IAHR2025 Word Congress – Singapore, 22-27 June 2025, with the following contribution Numerical modelling of surf zone hydrodynamics using SWASH;
- 11st SCACR2025 – Dubrovnik, 24-26 September 2025, with the following contribution Influence of spectral cut-off frequency on armour stability in shallow water (presented as oral presentation).
- 7th Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (EMCEI-2025) – Reggio Calabria, 23-26 June 2025, with the following contribution: *A Data-Driven Approach Considering Climate Change to Design Coastal and Port Defense Structures*.
- 1st International Online Conference on Marine Science and Engineering, 24-26 November 2025, with the following contribution: *Physical Modelling of Wave Overtopping Mitigation Through Adaptive Defence Solutions*.

SECTION 2 – PROGRESS OF ACTIVITIES

With regard to the specific timeframe (bi-monthly/end of project activities), it is below provided:

- a) detailed description of activities carried out by each operational unit with a focus on the timeframe for their implementation

The activities related to Task 1.1, Task 1.2 and Task 1.3 (WP1) was carried out by all the involved RUs, and they were completed at the end of the second four-month period. According to the project time schedule, the milestone M1.1 has been achieved and the deliverable D1.1 has been produced.

The activities related to the tasks of WP2 were carried out by UniCT (leader RU) and UniSALENTO. The theoretical basis of the algorithm for the calculation of the failure probability of the system were defined, and the programming codes for the implantation of Monte Carlo simulations were drafted by UniCT during the previous four-month periods (Task 2.1). Moreover, in the context of Task 2.2, two performance indexes, namely the ratio between the failure probability of the system and the maximum acceptance limit and the rate of growth of the failure probability, were defined by UniCT and UniSALENTO. The activities of the sixth four-month period focused on the definition of an economic index, which integrates the information provided by the performance indexes. A first attempt to employ the performance indexes to represent the spatial variability of the defense solution performances was made in the context of the activities of the Task 2.3 during the third four-month period, by applying the developed methodology to one of the possible upgrading options for the Catania harbor breakwater. During the fourth, fifth and sixth four-month period, the application to the case study of the Catania harbor breakwater was completed, including the estimate of the economic index and the evaluation of the effects of sea level rise (SLR) by 2070 and 2100 on the structure performances. In addition to this, during the sixth four-month period UniSALENTO and UniCT completed the application of the probabilistic method to the Italian case studies of the harbor rubble-mound breakwater of Arenella and the harbor vertical breakwater of Vado Ligure, which together with the case of the Port of Catania represent the three Italian case studies required to achieve the target T2. For both case studies, the performance and economic indexes were computed and the effects of SLR by 2070 and 2100 on the structure performances were evaluated. All the results of the activities of the WP2 are reported in the deliverable D2.1.

The activities related to the tasks of WP3 were carried out by UniNA and UniRC. In particular, during the sixth four-month period, UniNA determined the extreme wave conditions for the three Italian case studies previously mentioned, using the Copernicus projection datasets for two scenarios (i.e., RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). The significant wave heights for different return periods (ranging from 10 to 180 years) were inferred using the Peak Over Threshold (POT) procedure, with a threshold of 1.5 m and a minimum temporal gap of 12 hours between each extreme event. The analysis was performed for both directional sectors of 30 degrees and regardless of the wave direction. Furthermore, UniNA worked on the characterization of sea levels, especially on storm surge data, using both reanalysis and projection datasets. UniRC carried out the downscaling of both historical and projected datasets for the specific site of Vado Ligure using the numerical model SWAN. The offshore data were filtered by wave direction (ranging between 30°N and 200°N) and significant wave height ($H_s > 0.5$ m), resulting in fully filtered and propagated datasets. The wave propagation

was performed from offshore to a set of 24 nearshore points, located along the seaward alignment in proximity to the planned vertical breakwater at the site. Successively, UniNA has performed the multivariate analysis of propagated waves and sea levels during storm events (which have been detected by applying the Peak Over Threshold approach to the propagated time series). In particular, the analysis focused on the on the bivariate probability distributions of wave height/period and wave height/storm surge. Baseline and future projection results were compared to detect any effects of climate change. All the results of the activities of the WP3 are reported in the deliverable D3.1.

The activities related to WP4 were carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniNA the leader RU. UniNA and UniCT completed the Task 4.1 during the second four-month period, providing the basis for the definition of a methodology for the characterization of the deterioration level of existing defense solutions and for the selection of the most suitable adaptation options. The activities related to Task 4.3, Task 4.4, Task 4.5, and Task 4.6 were carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, RUs collected existing experimental and numerical data on damaged and upgraded harbor rubble-mound breakwaters, which includes both structure damage and wave overtopping, vertical wall breakwaters, seawalls and beach nourishments, considering their own data and available literature data. Moreover, UniCT conducted new experimental tests on upgraded rubble-mound breakwaters, in order to extend the existing dataset on this kind of structure. UniSALENTO and UniNA tested the effects of a beach nourishment in front of a vertical wall on wave/structure interaction processes, with particular reference to the overtopping phenomenon. Different grain size and geometry of the nourishment are being tested numerically using XBeach. Moreover, UniNA examined the capability of some adaptive solutions in reducing wave overtopping. In particular, the physical experiments concern vertical wall protected by rubble mound breakwaters combined with Reef Ball modules seated onto the crown. UniNA collected numerical and experimental data on these adaptive solutions, focusing on wave overtopping phenomenon. Finally, UniNA have analyzed long-shore sediment losses as a failure mechanism of beach nourishments. Numerical experiments have been used to verify some analytical solutions in case of a finite beach length (both open and enclosed coasts) concerning the time taken for a certain percentage of the initial fill volume to be lost. UniSALENTO contributed to the development of experimental and numerical datasets on rubble-mound breakwaters and seawalls, through laboratory tests on stability and advanced numerical modelling, including CFD simulations (OpenFOAM) for pressure analysis within the porous medium and XBeach simulations to investigate seawalls protected by beach nourishment, with a focus on wave overtopping and hydrodynamic response. All the results of the activities of the WP4 are reported in the deliverable D4.1.

The activities related to WP5 were carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, Task 5.1 (WP5) was carried out by UniCT and UniSALENTO (leader RU). During the sixth four-month period, material for the project web-platform, which is the deliverable D5.1, was organized, focusing on the information regarding the project and involved RUs and on the useful tools. As regards Task 5.2, all the RUs organized the final project meeting, which was held on 26th February 2026, therefore completing the deliverable D5.2. Task 5.3 was carried out by all the involved RUs. In particular, UniCT submitted the work “Wave overtopping of non-conventional rubble-mound breakwaters: blind comparison between experimental and numerical data” to the peer reviewed journal Ocean Engineering (in print) and the work “Probabilistic assessment of the performances of vertical breakwaters in a changing climate” for presentation at the 39th International Conference on Coastal Engineering 2026 (accepted). UniSALENTO attended to the 41st IAHR2025 Word Congress in Singapore and SCACR25 International Conference in Dubrovnik. Moreover, all the RUs are currently working for the submission of new research works to peer-reviewed journals, among which a joint paper based on the contents of the deliverable D1.1. Finally, UniCT launched the special issue

“Probabilistic Design in Coastal Engineering: Experience, Issues and Perspectives” in the Journal of Marine Science and Engineering, in order to collect new further contribute on the topic of the project.

The activities related to Task 6.1, Task 6.2 and Task 6.3 of WP6 were carried out by all the involved RUs, being UniCT the leader RU. The scientific and administrative management of the project (e.g. reporting, coordination, etc.) for technical development and financial monitoring was continuously performed by all the RUs. The deliverables D6.1 (Bi-monthly progress reports) and D6.2 (Meeting minutes) were finalized.

- b) description of potential changes to what has been originally approved mentioning the impacts on the aim of the intervention, on the achievement of intermediate and long-term goals, on the proposed actions for improvement;

Considering the extension of the Project deadline from 30th of November 2025 to the 28th of February 2026 (*see D.D. no. 1409 of the 14th of September 2022 - DECRETO DI PROROGA per la conclusione delle attività progettuali al 28 febbraio 2026*), the time schedule has been modified to allow the partners to deepen the ongoing analyses and to reinforce further cooperation among research units for joint work and publications, within a longer timeframe. In particular, as already stated in the report of the fifth four-month period, the following changes have been made:

- WP2: tasks 2.2 and 2.3, and consequently the milestones M2.1 and M2.2, the deliverable D2.1 and the target T2.1, were completed in February 2026;
- WP3: task 3.3, and consequently the milestone M3.2, the deliverable D3.1 and the target T3.1, were completed in January 2026;
- WP4: tasks 4.3, 4.4, 4.5 and 4.6, and consequently the milestone M4.2, the deliverable D4.1 and the target T4.1, were completed in January 2026;
- WP5: tasks 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3, and consequently the milestones M5.1, M5.2 and M5.3, the deliverables D5.1 and D5.2 and the targets T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3, were completed in February 2026;
- WP6: tasks 6.1 and 6.2, and consequently the milestones M6.1 and M6.2, the deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 and the target T6.1, were completed in February 2026.

- c) description of potential challenges encountered and of the proposed actions for improvement;

During the final phase of the project, the PI of UniSALENTO prof. A. Saponieri moved to the Polytechnic University of Bari. Consequently, the role of PI for UniSALENTO was assigned to Prof. G.R. Tomasicchio, who ensured full continuity of the project activities.

- d) brief description of potential publications.

In the context of the WP4, UniCT submitted to *Ocean Engineering* a paper, which has received minor revision, on the description of the hydraulic response of rubble-mound breakwaters in terms of wave overtopping, based on both experimental and numerical results. UniRC will contribute a paper presenting the structural response of vertical breakwaters consisting of interconnected caissons, able to transfer shear forces along the structure. The study will incorporate both experimental and theoretical study. Furthermore, UNIRC is about to publish a study that assesses the uncertainties related to the use of different databases as input. UniNA is working on a potential publication dealing with the role of some adaptive

solutions, such as seawalls protected by nourishment or rubble mound structures, in reducing the flooding risk of coastal areas. UniCT, UniNA and UniRC will prepare a paper on wave downscaling challenges. Finally, alle the RUs are started to work to a joint paper based on the contents of the deliverable D1.1.

Any relevant attached document which includes the abovementioned details

SECTION 3 – COMMON INDICATORS

Below the updates on the indicator RRFCI 8 – “*Number of researchers who work in research centres which are recipients of financial support (women; men; non-binary)*” – as per the description in the guidelines included in the n.34 MEF notification from the 17th of October 2022.

Common indicators	Planned value	Implemented value
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (women)	3	3
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (men)	7	7
Researchers who work in research centers which are recipients of financial support (non-binary)	0	0

SECTION 4 – PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS AND FINAL COMMENTS

Below it is provided a description of the forecast scenario on the development of the project, any potential change which is deemed necessary for the future as well as comments on the document.

1) Predictive analysis

The project activities were completed according to the time schedule updated considering the new Project deadline (i.e. February 2026).

2) Final comments

As already stated in the report of the fifth four-month period, the time schedule of the Project activities was updated considering the new final deadline of the 28th of February 2026. Indeed, although the project activities were proceeding as planned, the time schedule was been extended to allow the partners to deepen the ongoing analyses and to reinforce further cooperation among research units for joint work and publications, within a longer timeframe. No further changes to the scheduled activities and/or corrective actions for redefining the stated objectives were applied.

The Deputy Rector for Research

(digital signature)

ATTACHMENTS

The below documents are also attached to the technical – scientific report:

Att.1 – Declaration of compliance with DNSH principle and compliance with other principles as per the Environment code;

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